

4Q2 (4QGen-b) frag. 1 i + IAA Plate 1087 frag. 8

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The Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA) Museum Plate 1087 contains a strange mixture of fragments, to wit 4Q30 frags. 12, 14, 15, 26, 27, 43, and 44; 4Q33 7, 13, 14, and 15, as well as in the top two rows of the plate seven fragments that seem not to have been published in the DJD series. I identified two of those seven fragments as belonging to the Exodus manuscripts 4Q13 (4QExod^b) and 4Q14 (4QExod^c), and surmised that all seven unpublished fragments might belong to pentateuchal manuscripts.¹ Since many of the fragments on Plate 1087 were photographed in 1959 and 1960 in the photographs of other plates, one must assume that Plate 1087 was constituted later in the 1960s. One or more of the editors brought together a range of fragments which had been identified as Pentateuch fragments. This may have been Frank Moore Cross, since the Pentateuch manuscripts written in Aramaic script had been assigned to him, or John Strugnell who continued identifying unidentified fragments throughout the 1960s and 1970s.

On the supposition that the unpublished fragments all belong to Pentateuchal manuscripts, it is not difficult to read and identify PAM 1087 frag. 8.

IAA Pl. 187 frag. 8 (photo Shai Halevi; digitization Maruf Shali)

One may read

]היר.[1
]קיע.[2

The traces at the beginning of line 1 are compatible with *yod*, and that at the beginning of line 2 with *resh*. Out of context one would not know whether the letter after *qoph* would be *waw* or *yod*. The textual remains suffix to consider the text of Gen 1:6-7, which facilitates the manuscript identi-

¹See my "Another 4Q14 fragment (IAA Plate 1087 frag. 6)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5599179>

fication: the script is identical to that of 4Q2, and the fragment joins to 4Q2 1 i in the top right fragment.²

A tear runs through the middle of the fragment separating the two parts of *yod* and distorting the form of the fragment. With Gimp I selected the top left part of the fragment, rotated it a few degrees and moved it to close the gap between the two parts of *yod*. This restored form of the fragment joins very neatly, textually and materially to 4Q2 1 i, as is shown by the following image:

IAA Plate 215 frag. 1 and IAA Plate 1087 frag. 8 (bottom left)
photographs Shai Halevi; joined with Gimp

The bottom part of the fragment joins to the main large piece of 4Q2 frag. 1, which also preserved the bottom tip of the *qoph*.

²For another fragment to be joined to 4Q2 frag. 1 see my “4Q2 (4QGen-b) frag. 1 ii + frag. 4.” <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5590071>

Thus, this small fragment from Pl. 1087 connects the two major parts of 4Q2 frag. 1. With this fragment, 4Q2 1 i lines 6-7 may be transcribed as follows:

[ויאמר] אלהים יהי ר[קיע בתוך המים ויהי מב] דיל בין [מים למים ויעש] 6
[אלהים את ה] רקיע [וי] ב[ד] ל [ב]י[ן] המים אשר מתחת לרק[יע ובין המים] 7